

TAALWETENSCHAP

Teacher who will receive this document: Dra. Judith Holler and Dr James Trujillo

Title of document: An Analysis of head movements and social actions: an analysis of Conversations

Name of course: Master's thesis language variation and multilingualism

Date of submission: 06.30.2023

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A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Isis Abril Pérez Gallegos', written in a cursive style.

Name of student: Isis Abril Pérez Gallegos

Student number:S1099180

Radboud University

An Analysis of Head Movements and Social Actions

An analysis of conversations

Name: Isis Abril Pérez Gallegos

Student Number: S1099180

Date: June 30th , 2023

Course: Thesis Master in Language Variation and
Multilingualism

Supervisors: Dr Judith Holler and Dr James Trujillo

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to dedicate this paper to everyone who was part of this process. First, I want to thank my supervisors who helped a lot during this process and gave me the opportunity to be part of such an amazing project. Second, to all my family, who supported me to come here even when that meant crying and missing each other every day. To my parents, who gave me the strength and the advice to manage new challenges, for making me laugh during every call and always remind how capable I am to achieve what I want, I know I couldn't have done this without you. To my brother, for teaching what happiness is by always being himself, for all the crazy conversations and most of all, for giving me his love and support even when we were so far away. To my boyfriend, who changed my life in a crazy way but always helped me to overcome every challenge I was facing and for making me realize that everything is possible even if that requires sweat and tears. And finally, to myself, for being brave enough to keep going even when everything felt like was not worth it or impossible. To all of you, thank you...

ABSTRACT

Different visual signals, such as manual gestures in natural settings aid rapid comprehension and timely response in communication. Previous research highlights the impact of body movements on the communication process. Social actions also play a vital role in meaning comprehension. This study investigates the influence of head gestures (nods and shakes) on underlying intentions and their alignment with social actions. We analyse head motions during uncontrolled face-to-face conversations, focusing on vertical and horizontal movements. Our findings illuminate how social actions shape head movements, facilitating the conveyance of meaning in interactions. Using a corpus of dyadic conversations with manual annotations, we explore the presence of head movements in a natural conversation. These findings will help us to understand the extent to which our goals influence how we move, as well as unrevealing the intricate connection between head gestures and social actions. This research contributes to our broader understanding of visual signs in communicative dynamics and provides insights into the mechanism by which meaning is conveyed in interactions.

Keywords: head gestures, conversation analysis, social actions, questions, responses

INTRODUCTION

Human conversations are a complex interplay of language and nonverbal clues, transcending mere words. While spoken language forms the backbone of communication, various gestures and movements also contribute significantly to the understanding and transmission of messages in conversations. Numerous authors have emphasized the significance of body movements in face-to-face interactions, shedding light on their crucial role. The present research specifically focuses on head movements, aiming to establish a connection between these subtle shifts and social actions within conversations. For this purpose, in this introduction, we will define the concepts of head gestures and social actions.

Social actions are defined as the communicative functions performed by utterances during conversations (Atkinson et al., 1984). Examples of social actions include questioning, responding, and stating. Recognizing and identifying the intended social action of a speaker at an early stage can significantly narrow down the potential range of statements they might make. Additionally, Weber (1978) defines social action as encompassing the behaviours, effects, and consequences of human actions, which, in turn, can influence the behaviour of others. Social action is instrumental in achieving specific goals within social interactions and can trigger means and ends for social actors and their interactions. This, in turn, facilitates rapid comprehension of the intended message and enables timely response formulation for the speakers (Nota et al., 2021).

Wittgenstein (1953) and Austin (1962), explain that speaking is not solely a descriptive or indexical activity aimed at representing the world. Rather, by speaking we are acting in it, encompassing a wide range of behavioural and performative aspects. Similarly, further studies by Drew (2013) explain that during a conversation there is more than the message, the other half of interaction is action. Additionally, Levinson (2013) explains that language does not deliver meaning but instead delivers actions. These studies collectively shed light on the crucial role of action within language usage, commonly referred to as social action.

In addition to social actions, body movements are crucial components of human interactions. Studies by Argyle (2013), Mehrabian (2017), and Higo et al. (2014) have highlighted the contributions of body movements to effective communication, emphasizing their role in understanding the messages in conversations. Previous research has also demonstrated a relationship between intentions and movement kinematics. (e.g., Cavallo et al., 2016; Trujillo and Holler, 2021; Sartori et al., 2011). While numerous studies have examined several types of gestures, such as hand movements (Krauss et al., 1991; Beattie and Shovelton, 1999), torso (Trujillo and Holler, 2021), and head movements (Trujillo and Holler, 2021). These studies have shown that movement kinematics can form the basis for the detection of intention in conversations.

Dittmann and Llewellyn (1968) found that listeners tended to nod and vocalize at the boundaries of the speaker's phonemic clauses. Showing two main patterns: nodding and

vocalizing before making a comment or asking a question and nodding and vocalizing in response to the speaker's direct questions and more perfunctory expressions.

Given the rapid processing of social actions during unfolding utterances, visual cues, such as head motions, may play a significant role in signaling social actions (Nota et al., 2021). Understanding the complex link between head motions and social acts might help us gain a more complete understanding of face-to-face contact and its multimodal character.

The role of nonverbal communication in face-to-face interaction has received significant attention in research. Among the various nonverbal cues, head gestures have been identified as an intriguing area of study. By head gestures we mean the expressive movements of the head while speaking. Previous research has established a connection between head movements and linguistic structure (Birdwhistell, 1970). Studies have indicated that individuals tend to exhibit continuous head movements while speaking, which become still during pauses and when listening (Hadar et al., 1983). This suggests that head movements are closely correlated with speech, much like the relationship between manual gestures and speech. Speakers often use their hands and limbs while listeners remain relatively still. Moreover, head nodding and shaking, known as head gestures, have been recognized as conventional gesture emblems in various cultural contexts, supplementing or even replacing verbal expressions of agreement, disagreement, or attitudes such as approval or disapproval (Fusaro et al., 2012).

The discourse structure of an utterance has also been found to be connected to certain head movements (Kendon, 1972). Different patterns of bodily movements vary according to the communicative purpose of the utterance. For instance, the speaker's head posture differs when introducing the main focus of the discourse compared to parenthetical remarks. Moreover, bodily movements are classified as gestures when they possess an "exclusionary" nature, meaning they return to their initial orientation after the movement (Kendon, 2002).

While several studies have examined the functions of communicative head movements, such as marking the contrast between formal and functional terms (Heylen, 2006), propositional content and semantic meaning (McClave, 2000), referring to objects by pointing with the head in space (Goodwin, 1981), eliciting feedback from dialogue partners (Heldner et al., 2013), and encouraging speaker engagement, the study of head movements is complex (Wagner et al., 2014). Head movements have relatively more freedom compared to speech forms but are more constrained than manual gestures (Malisz et al., 2016).

As mentioned before, previous research on visual signals in communication, particularly gesture in multimodal communication, has predominantly focused on gaze, hand motions, head movements, and related gestures (Beattie and Shovelton, 1999, 2002; Griffin, 2004; Rimé and Schiaratura, 1991; Thompson and Massaro, 1986). However, these studies often neglect spontaneous and genuine discussions, favouring controlled experimental settings.

Several studies have emphasized the significance of the frequency of bodily movements during conversations. These studies have specifically examined the distribution of movements throughout a conversation and their correlation with the verbal context expressed (McNeill, 1993), encompassing both gestures and speech (Bergmann and Kopp, 2006).

The studies mentioned in this introduction show the extensive research that has been done on body gestures in conversations and social actions. However, there is a scarcity of research focusing on the potential connection between these two elements. Recently, Trujillo and Holler (2021) introduced research that explores the potential relationship between social actions and body signals in communication, being the first one to investigate how movement is shaped by the social action performed by an utterance, providing a foundational basis for the current study.

The present study takes a step further by delving into the underlying social implications of these gestures in conversations. By analysing the frequency of head gestures in questions and responses, we can uncover the meaning embedded within these movements and explore their role in face-to-face interactions. Head movements could give us an idea of how the conversation will develop and signal the intentions underlying social actions

Head movements could give us an idea of how the conversation will develop and signal the intentions underlying social actions. However, despite the acknowledgement that head movements are present in conversations and play a significant role in interactions, their specific significance within the context of questions and responses and how they may help the

The existing literature is limited in scope as it often relies on diverse types of interactions, such as phone calls or play roles, which lack the factors and variables of face-to-face conversations. Therefore, there is a gap in our understanding regarding the role of head movements in the specific context of questions and responses during genuine, unscripted interactions.

The present study aims to address this gap by answering the following research questions “What is the frequency of head gestures in questions and responses during Dutch face-to-face conversations? (2) How do lateral and vertical head gestures (shakes and nods) align with various categories of social action performed through questions? And are there significant differences in the distributions across the social actions in questions.” More specifically, we analyse an extensive dyad corpus where social actions (SA) in questions were previously annotated, and then we create manual annotations of the head gestures, concretely vertical and lateral movements, present in the conversations to look for a possible relationship between the occurrence of SA and head movements.

While the concepts of non-verbal gestures and social actions have been discussed across diverse contexts, this paper specifically delves into their application within the realm of linguistics, with a focused lens of pragmatics and conversational analysis. By delving into these fields, we aim to elucidate the relevance and implications of head gestures and social actions in understanding the intricacies of communication. It would analyse if head gestures have a relationship with the social actions occurring in questions and answers and if they have an intention regarding the social actions in the conversation.

THE PRESENT STUDY

In this study, we aimed to investigate the role of head gestures in multimodal face-to-face interactions, focusing on their frequency and relationship with social actions., by doing this we would find if head movements were shaped by the social actions in conversations. To achieve this, we utilized the Dutch conversation corpus as the data source. According to previous studies, this study is one of the first ones that explores the connection between head movements and social actions. The primary research objectives were to address two key questions: (1) What is the frequency of head gestures in questions and responses during Dutch face-to-face conversations? (2) How do lateral and vertical head gestures align with distinct categories of social action performed through questions? and are there significant differences in the distributions across the social actions in questions? Based on these inquiries, numerous hypotheses about the role of head gestures in conversations were developed. To begin, it was expected that head movements would be prominent in both questions and responses, having a similar percentage of total gestures between nods and shakes. Second, it was projected that shakes and nods would correspond with particular social actions stated questions, having a higher number of head gestures present occurring especially in mutual understanding (MU), request for information (RI), and active participation (AP), this hypothesis is not supported from previous research since as mentioned before, the existing literature is limited. Finally, the distribution of head movements was predicted to be shaped by the social actions occurring simultaneously and have a meaningful relationship between both categories. By exploring these elements, this study offers a new perspective on the analysis of body movements in conversations and the connection to social actions in questions and responses.

METHODS

It is important to mention that this study was done based on the existing corpus and previous studies. Consequently, some of the descriptions of the corpus, equipment, and previous annotations are part of existing research. However, these elements played an important role in the current study and its explanation was important for the understanding of the analysis of the data.

Corpus and Participants

The current research employed thirty-four dyads that comprise a multimodal Dutch face-to-face conversation corpus (CoAct corpus) supervised by Dr Judith Holler. During the recording, pairs of Dutch native speakers (mean age: 23.10 \pm 8 years females, 17, males) engaged in casual conversations for an hour. None of the participants had motor or language impairments and all had normal or corrected-to-normal vision.

The recording session was split into three sections, with each one lasting between 20 to 25 minutes. This study examined the first part of the conversation, which involved an unguided and open-ended dialogue.

Prior to starting the recording session, participants were instructed to hold a T-pose for three seconds in order to calibrate the motion tracking software (Kinect for Windows 2, Brekel Pro Face 2.39, Brekel Pro Body 2.48, and Wireshark) and to clap in order to synchronize the audible and visual information.

Informed consent was obtained before and after filming. Before the study, participants were required to complete a demographics questionnaire. At the end of the study, they were asked to fill out four additional questionnaires. These questionnaires included inquiries about the quality of the conversation and the relationship between the participants, as well as the Empathy Quotient (Baron-Cohen and Wheelwright, 2004) and the Fear of Negative Evaluation Scale (Watson and Friend, 1969). Participants were also asked to rate how well they understood the explicit goal of the experiment. The current study did not make use of the data acquired from these surveys. As a token of appreciation, participants were given a reward of 18 euros at the conclusion of the session. The corpus study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the Social Science department at Radboud University Nijmegen, with the approval code ECSW 2018-124.

There are several reasons why this method and specific corpus were selected to conduct the study. Firstly, the existing corpus offers the opportunity to analyse natural conversations,

assuring better reliability to what a conversation in a natural environment is. Secondly, previous annotations in the corpus help the efficacy of the study. Finally, analysis of the corpus and the creation of annotations in ELAN help the understanding of the topic and create a reliable source of information.

Equipment

The conversation took place in a soundproof room located at the Max Planck Institute of Psycholinguistics in Nijmegen, Netherlands. Participants were seated facing each other. With a distance of approximately 90 cm from the front edge of the seats. Various cameras were used to record the interactions. Two cameras (Canon XE405) captured frontal views of each participant, while two other cameras recorded each participant's body from a 45-degree angle (Canon XF205 Camcorder). Two additional cameras (Canon XF205 Camcorder) were positioned overhead on tripods to record a bird's-eye view of each participant. Lastly, one camera (Canon Legria HF G10) recorded the overall scene, displaying both participants simultaneously. All cameras recorded at a frame rate of twenty-five frames per second (fps). The audio was recorded using two directional microphones (Sennheiser me-64) for each participant. Each recording session resulted in seven video files and two audio files, which were synchronized and combined into a single audio file for analysis in Adobe Premiere Pro CS6 (MPEG,25fps). This resulted in a time resolution of approximately forty ms, equivalent to the duration of a single frame. For the coding of head gestures in the present study, the close-up and body footage of the participants was utilized.

Data Annotation

Head gestures

The criteria used to identify head gestures in this study were derived from the comprehensive framework presented in “The Active Listening Corpus (ALICO) (Malisz, et. al., 2016). ALICO serves as a valuable resource that provides deep insights into the exploration of multimodal and cognitive phenomena exhibited by listeners in spontaneous dialogues. It not only sheds light on the intricate dynamics of human communication but also enables the examination of reciprocal influences between dialogue partners. In this study we annotated the head movements during the full conversation, however, our analysis was focused on the questions and responses aligned gestures.

In our study, we specifically focused on examining head movements, which played a significant role in participants’ conversational behaviour. These movements included vertical nods and lateral shakes. To ensure the precision and accuracy of our annotations, we intentionally excluded movements that resulted from activities such as swallowing, inhaling, gradual postural shifts, tics, laughter, and other non-meaningful sources. By doing so, we aimed to isolate and focus solely on the head gestures that carried communicative intent.

The specific head gestures we considered for annotation included rotation down-up, also known as nods, reversed nod up-down, referred to as jerks. If there was a repetitive movement (e.g., down-up-down, up-down-up) was also annotated as a nod. On the other hand, repetitive turning (e.g., lateral turning), was categorized as shake. It is important to mention that during the annotation process, we treated the jerk gesture as a nod in both the annotations and subsequent data analysis.

To maintain consistency and clarity, we established certain categorization guidelines for head movements. For instance, isolated movements such as turning the head to one side and not returning, as well as tilting or inking the head, were not classified as shakes (refer to Figure 1.1 for a detailed description of head movements by ALICO).

Furthermore, we took into account the duration and context of head gestures. Nods were not considered if the chin remained in a raised position throughout the entire gesture. Additionally, if a head gesture was accompanied by other movements, such as laughing,

touching the hair, or directing the gaze elsewhere, we only annotated it if there was a clear nod or shake occurring. This ensured that the annotations focused on the essential communicative head movements, filtering out potential confounding factors.

To carry out the meticulous annotation process, we adopted a frame-by-frame approach, meticulously analyzing each frame to identify and mark the presence of head gestures. This detailed analysis was facilitated by the utilization of ELAN software (version 5.5), which provided a reliable platform for organizing and categorizing the annotations.

Head Gesture	Definition
Nods	Rotation down-up
Jerks	Reversed nod, up-down
Shakes	Repeated turning
Tilt	Rotation left or right
Bobble	Repeated tilting sideways
Turn	Turning left or right
Protrusion	Pushing the head forward
Retraction	Pulling the head back
Slide	Translation left or right
Shift	Repeated horizontal slides
Waggle	Irregular connected movement

Figure 1. Description of head movements according to ALICO

Figure 2. Schematic overview of rotations and translations along three axes as well as an example of movements most frequently used in communicative head gesturing (taken from ALICO corpus)

Questions and responses

The questions and responses have previously been manually annotated. Using the Bavarian Archive for Speech Signals Webservices (Kisler et al., 2017), an automated orthographic transcription of the speech was completed. The manual annotations were completed using ELAN (5.5) and the coding method created by Stivers and Enfield (2010). However, a comprehensive strategy was used to account for the intricacy of the corpus data, taking into account visual physical cues, context phrasing, intonation, and addressee behavior. Sighs and other nonverbal noises like laughing were not included in the research. The entire process involved two human coders, one being a native speaker of Dutch, and the other a highly proficient Dutch speaker.

Social actions

The identification of social actions was achieved by a thorough investigation of multiple elements. The analysis included a look at how the question was phrased, how they were placed in the conversation in order, and how much common ground was formed between the speaker and the interlocutor. The speaker's underlying objectives or aims, their precise intents behind the inquiry, the utterance's outcomes, and even the structural form of the question itself, were all considered.

A classification system was created to offer a structured foundation for classifying these social actions. The acts were divided not only into broad categories but also into more specific sub-categories.

It is important to note that, despite not being the primary topic of the current study, these sub-categories allowed for a more detailed analysis of the diverse range of social actions observed. Examples of these categories include but are not limited to, requests for information, interactions promoting mutual understanding, active participation, and references to shared information (see full description of the social action, Fig. 3).

Categories	Definition
RI	Request for information
OIR	Other-initiated repair
MU	Mutual understanding
EAS	Evaluative/affiliative/stance
PA	Plans and actions
AP	Active participation
NDOS	Not directed at other speaker
SIMCA	Structuring, initiating or maintaining conversational action

Figure 3. Description of Social Actions Categories

Statistical analysis

In order to obtain the frequency of head gestures per social action, we obtained the total of head gestures and then categorized them into nods and shakes, obtaining the total number of head gestures per social action in each category (nod and shake).

The data analysis consisted of linear mixed-effects models employed using the Lme4 (Bates et al., 2015) package in R. This approach allowed for the examination of the main effects of head gestures, specifically focusing on their frequency and overlap with social actions. Additionally, the interaction between participants was incorporated as a random factor in the model.

In the analysis, we used two sets of linear mixed models. One model included only utterance duration as a covariate while the second model include utterance duration and social action to account for the presence of head gestures. By utilizing linear mixed-effects models, it became possible to account for the inherent variability among participants and their interactions. The Lme4 package in R facilitated the inclusion of participant-specific random

effects, enabling the modelling of individual differences and the consideration of the interplay between participants within the conversational context.

In order to be able to obtain the expected results we processed the data in Python (v.3.7) obtaining the frequency of head gestures that overlap partially and fully with different social actions.

In order to account for any intrinsic variation in speech length across or within social action categories, utterance duration was incorporated. All analyses were performed in R (R Core Team, 2019.p.4). A likelihood ratio test of model comparison was used in order to compare the effects of utterance duration in the results while testing for an effect of social action, emmeans was used for post hoc comparisons, and sjPot was used for visualization of the results.

RESULTS

This study's main goal was to investigate the complex link between various categories of social actions and head gestures. This was accomplished by conducting a rigorous analysis using linear mixed models to examine the correlation between the frequency of head gestures and the observed social actions.

First research question

Addressing our initial research question, we meticulously gathered data on the occurrence of head movements within dyadic interactions. Out of the extensive collection of 2528 files, files referring to the conversations were obtained, from which we then got a notable subset of 403 files that included head gestures. This subset provided a rich foundation for examining the association between head gestures and social actions.

A more detailed examination revealed that there was a total of 430 gestures observed, 182 cases were categorized as nods, while the remaining instances belonged to the category of shakes.

To facilitate a distinct understanding of gesture separation, we undertook an analysis of head gestures in relation to each specific social action (SA) category, as presented in Table 1. Subsequently, we classified these gestures into nods and shakes, which are outlined separately in Tables 2 and 3, respectively.

Table 1. Total head gestures per SA

Social Action Category	Head gestures
PA	3
SIMCA	8
AP	17
OIR	20
EAS	56
NDOS	73
MU	109
RI	144

Table 2. Total nods per SA

Social Action Category	Nods
PA	1
SIMCA	4
AP	7
OIR	11
EAS	18
NDOS	19
RI	59
MU	63

Table 3. Total shakes per SA

Social Action Category	Shakes
PA	2
SIMCA	2
OIR	6
AP	10
EAS	26
MU	35
NDOS	40
RI	70

Second research question

In order to answer our second research question, we carried out a linear mixed model in R studio. We create two models, the null model included utterance duration as a predictor and files as a random effect. On the other hand, the full model included utterance duration and social action as variable while keeping files as random effects.

The null model showed a REML criterion of 2414.2. The scaled residuals indicated some deviations between the observed data and the model's predictions, with a range from -2.3328 to 8.1419.

The random effects analysis revealed significant variability in the head gesture frequency between different files, as indicated by the estimated variance of 0.01903 (SD= 0.1379) for the random intercepts. The residual variance component, representing unexplained variability within each file, was estimated to be 0.14481 (SD= 0.3805).

The fixed effects in the null model revealed a significant effect for the utterance duration predictor (Estimate = 0.0608, SE= 0.079, t=7.733, p<0.001).

The second model (null model) included utterance and social action as variables. This model showed a REML criterion of 2439.2. The scaled residuals showed a deviation between the observed data and the model's prediction, from -2.2319 to 8.1543.

The random effects analysis indicates significant variability in the head gestures between the different files, with a variance of 0.01913 (SD=0.1383) for the random intercepts. The residual variance component, representing unexplained variability within each file, was estimated to be 0.14455 (SD=0.3802).

The full model, which included utterance duration and SA, only the utterance duration predictor showed a significant effect (Estimate =0.0576, SE= 0.0083, t=6.908, p<0.001). While none of the additional variables (SA, SAAP, SAEAS, SAMU, SANDOS, SAOIR, SAPA, SARI, SASIMCA) demonstrated significant effects (all p>0.05).

To compare the validity of both models, we performed a likelihood ratio test of model comparison (ANOVA). The null model demonstrated a slightly better fit to the data compared to the full model. The null model yielded an AIC value of 2408.2 and a BIC value of 2431.6, with a log-likelihood of -1200.1 and deviance of 2400.2. The full model had an AIC of 2412.1 and a BIC of 2482.1, with a log-likelihood of -1194.0 and deviance of 2388.1. The chi-square test comparing the null model and the full model showed a non-significant result ($\chi^2 = 12.147$, df =8, p =0.1448), indicating that there was no significant difference in model fit between the two models.

Figure 6. Figure A shows the relationship between social action (x-axis) and the occurrence of head gestures frequency, represented by head_gest_frequency (y-axis)

DISCUSSION

The findings of this research have provided valuable and novel insights into the role of head movements in conveying distinct social action categories within a conversational context.

The results of our first question showed that there might be a link between the presence of social action and the head gestures since specific actions had a higher presence of head gestures (e.g., RI, MU, NDOS, and EAS) matching partially with our hypothesis since we expected a higher match in RI, MU and AP. Even after categorizing the head gestures between nods and shakes we obtained comparable results, with MU and Ri being the more present. However, the results of our second question suggest a meaningful relationship between head gesture frequency and utterance duration, indicating that longer utterances are associated with increased head gestures. However, the inclusion of social actions did not provide additional explanatory power, suggesting that they may not substantially contribute to head gesture frequency in this context.

The findings of our study suggest a potential association between social actions and head gestures, as indicated by the results of our first question. However, the second analysis revealed that the duration of an utterance significantly influences these findings. It is observed that the duration of an utterance can create opportunities for an increased frequency of head gestures, irrespective of the social action present during that specific time. Given the result that utterance duration plays a crucial role in facilitating the occurrence of head gestures, independent of the concurrent social actions.

Our investigation has shed light on the subtle nature of head gestures in interpersonal interactions, revealing that the function of the utterance (i.e., social action) is associated with the frequency of head gestures. It can be considered for further research that other factors may take part in this connection, such as the speaker's intention, the perceived aim or purpose of the utterance, observed social behavior, and possibly other yet-undiscovered variables. Through our study, we have uncovered the intricate connections between head movements and social actions, thereby highlighting the profound role of bodily communication in human interaction.

Interestingly, the results of our study align with those obtained by Trujillo and Holler (2021), wherein no significant contrast was found between social actions. This convergence of findings supports the notion that the relationship between head gestures and social actions is a complex and multifaceted one, requiring further exploration.

Despite the intriguing insights provided by our research, it is important to emphasize that we did not establish a statistically significant link between head gestures and all social actions. This suggests the presence of other variables at play or potential variations within specific social action categories that were not accounted for in our study. Thus, it is imperative that future research endeavours delve deeper into these aspects to gain a more comprehensive understanding.

Furthermore, future studies could also explore the potential influence of cultural and individual differences on head gestures and their alignment with social actions. The influence of culture in the meaning of head gestures during conversations has also been previously

analyzed (e.g., Maynard, 1987) explains that Japanese speakers do not nod within an utterance for interactional purposes, their nods occur either on the last syllable of speech during (potential) turn-transition pauses, while according to McClave (1999) shows that American speakers use head gestures as modality markers for uncertainty, and they also signal discourse structure by introducing direct quotes, they also have a deictic function, and lexical repairs that are kinesically marked. By incorporating a cross-cultural perspective and considering the variability across individuals, researchers can shed further light on the contextual and personal factors that shape head movements during conversations.

Future studies should consider the limitations encountered in our research. This approach will enable the identification of potential patterns and variations that may emerge, providing a more nuanced understanding of the intricate dynamics between body gestures and social actions.

LIMITATIONS

Despite its substantial contributions, the current study has some limitations that should be taken into account for future research.

Firstly, the visibility of head movements can be influenced by other accompanying movements, making it challenging to isolate and accurately interpret head gestures. To assure the accuracy of our findings, we made a conscious effort to code only those head gestures that were clearly distinguishable and were not masked by other movements. The diversity of the gestural repertory, however, makes it vital to understand that certain subtle or nuanced head gestures might have gone unnoticed or been misunderstood.

Secondly, the various levels of familiarity among the participants are a significant factor that was not fully taken into consideration in this study. The level of familiarity between people can affect interpersonal dynamics, communication preferences, and the types of motions involved (Feyereisen, 2002). As familiarity may contribute extra nuances and variability to the observed patterns, future studies should consider investigating how familiarity impacts

the occurrence and interpretation of head gestures, as it may introduce additional factors and variability into the observed patterns.

Furthermore, it is crucial to understand that the study of head gestures and how they relate to social actions and how they relate to social behaviour is still in the early stage. As a result, there is a relatively little amount of existing literature to consult when deciding on the proper sample size for investigations in this field. It is vital to recognize that the sample size might not accurately reflect the range and complexity of head movements in all social circumstances, despite the efforts to recruit a sufficient sample size based on resources and practicality. To improve the generalizability of results and guarantee a more thorough understanding of the subject, future studies might examine larger and more varied populations.

Despite the fact that the current study has shed light on the connection between head gestures and social actions, its shortcomings must be acknowledged and addressed. By addressing the challenges related to the visibility of head movements, accounting for varying levels of familiarity among participants, and expanding the sample size in future research, we can further enhance the validity and generalizability of findings in this fascinating field of study.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the primary objective of our study was to examine the influence of social actions on head gestures within questions and responses during naturalistic conversations. Through our analysis, we have gained significant insight into the intricate elements that shape and influence head gestures in the context of interpersonal communication.

Our research has shown the strong link between head movements and social actions and the value of nonverbal clues in enhancing the depth of human communication. Nevertheless, it is crucial to recognize that much more research has to be done in this area.

Future research should consider expanding the scope to better understand the complex nature of head gestures and their impact on molding human communication. Researchers can examine the phenomenon in more depth by using larger corpora and a variety of analytical tools. With this method, we can discover more variations and intricate details that could help us gain a deeper knowledge of how head motions are used in social interactions.

Our study has provided valuable insights into the relationship between head gestures and social actions within naturalistic conversations. However, more investigations into this complicated phenomenon are required to identify the process that shapes head movements in human communication.

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